

FoodPackLab 2.0

Deep Tech-Packaging Partnership for Food Innovation

Del 5.1. FoodPackLab 2.0 monitoring scoreboard

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 5.1. – Monitoring scoreboard - aims to provide an instrument to monitor project activities and their timings. The main purpose is to point out if the activities are on time, and, in case of a delay, it enables the consortium to react on time and, eventually, to activate the appropriate contingency plan.

Moreover, the sketch of a scoreboard to monitor the efficacy of the events organized for SMEs and matchmaking sessions has been proposed.

2. The monitoring tools

Monitoring is an important tool that enables to control the timing of the different project activities and their effectiveness, in order to get the best results and reach the project goals as designed in the proposal.

The basic idea is to implement a tool to compare over the time the actual performance with those planned to measure the actual results against expected KPI.

To accomplish this goal, the first task of WP5 is thus the design of a project scoreboard, in order to analyse the support provided to the SMEs and its outcomes.

We then designed a detailed workflow to monitor the efficacy of the events organized for SMEs and in particular the matchmaking events.

3. The project scoreboard

The project scoreboard has been designed taking into account the project KPIs.

It is represented as a table: in the columns it is written the Indicator that has to be monitored (e.g. number of webinars), the work package they are related to, the leader of that work package, the target as written in the proposal and the monitoring month. In order to assure a correct timing of all the activities, we decided to monitor each indicator every 3 months.

The scoreboard has been validated by the consortium members during the second online meeting of the project which took place on November 6, 2020

In the following two pages, the final project scoreboard is presented.

100% of the objective on the period

50%

10%

WP n°	WP Leader	Indicators	Description	Target									Total to date
					M3	M6	M9	M12	M15	M18	M21	M24	
1	SECPHO	Number of project reports prepared	Call KPI	3									
1	SECPHO	Number of partnership consortium meetings	Call KPI	24									
2	Systematic	Number of communication packages	Call KPI	1									
2	Systematic	Number of social media followers	Call KPI	200									
2	Systematic	Number of Newsletters	Call KPI	6									
3	Packaging cluster	Number of cluster organisations and business networks from different COSME participating countries having benefited from the supported actions	Call KPI	20									
3	Packaging cluster	Number of partnership agreements resulting from the supported actions	Call KPI	12									
3	Packaging cluster	Number of resulting cooperation projects between international cluster and business network partners	Call KPI	3									
3	Packaging cluster	Number of factfinding missions	Call KPI	2									
3	Packaging cluster	Number of MoU signed between the Partnership and international partners	Call KPI	5									
4	SECPHO	Number of business agreements resulting from the supported actions	Call KPI	4									
4	PACK4FOOD	Number of webinars	Call KPI	3									
4	SECPHO	Number of internationalization missions organized	Call KPI	3									

2,3,4		Number of events organised	Call KPI	9									
4	SECPHO	Number of cluster and business matchmaking meetings supported	Call KPI	150									
5	VITAGORA	Increase in the percentage of the turnover from international activities, and employment in Europe, of the SMEs having benefited directly and indirectly from the supported actions, as measured through a survey by the end of the action.	Call KPI	1-5%									
5	VITAGORA	Number of monitoring surveys		1									
		Number of monitoring surveys answers		135									
5	PACK4FOOD	Number of roadmaps for partnerships		1									
5	VITAGORA	Number of SMEs having directly or indirectly benefited from the supported actions, resulting in cooperation projects		45									

4. The workpackage scoreboard

It has also been discussed the opportunity to design and set up a more detailed scoreboard, one for each work package and eventually with a faster monitoring timing.

The idea is to have one scoreboard (e.g. in a one Excel sheet included in a file named "whole project scoreboard") to monitor the progress of the single work package and to put the results of this single wp scoreboard in the project monitoring table described in the previous paragraph.

As an example we created an excel sheet for WP1. It is possible to fill in the cells with the dates of consortium meeting. The total number of meeting every 3 months is automatically calculated in the project scoreboard line 2. We can create similar sheet for the 5 WPs of the project. By doing this, we have a strict monitoring of the activities of all the WPs and of the whole project.

	M3			M6			M9			M12			M15		
Project report date															
Consortium meeting dates															

5. The event scoreboard

During these first months of the project, we designed a workflow that will be useful to monitor the activities devoted to SMEs and matchmaking events. Due to the current pandemic situation, we are considering that the events can run online, instead of in presence as planned in the proposal; or both online and live. For this reason, we prepared a double workflow that can be used in both the situation. The main points and information that we can obtain from this workflow is: the participant info and how he/she was engaged in the project. By doing so, we can measure the efficacy of the project dissemination and communication activities and eventually include the company in the database. Other information are related to the organization of the event: the location, accessibility, also comfort and food play an important role in the overall impression of the event and of the consortium, and can facilitate matchmaking between the invited companies. As a last point from the workflow we get information on the matchmaking event itself: e.g. how many new contacts we created.

All the information presented in the workflow will be organized as a survey, that will be used in SMEs interview to keep their feedback on projects activities. The results of the survey will objectively design the events (and project) effectiveness and will be useful in identifying and studying the lesson learned. In the following pages we represent the workflow that is at the basis of the survey to SMEs.

The scoreboard was developed considering a matrix that embraces both temporal aspects and specific needs based on different scenarios (e.g., limitations due to COVID-19).

A first draft of the scoreboard's key elements was based on a Customer Satisfaction approach (CSAT), comparing the project's goals with the expectation and the outcome of the final user, as a customer¹.

¹ Fryer, K., Antony, J. and Ogden, S. (2009), "Performance management in the public sector", International Journal of Public Sector Management, Vol. 22 No. 6, pp. 478-498. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513550910982850>,

Lilian Chan, Y. (2004), "Performance measurement and adoption of balanced scorecards: A survey of municipal governments in the USA and Canada", International Journal of Public Sector Management, Vol. 17 No. 3, pp. 204-221. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513550410530144>

In this sense, the approach aims to assess both partners' internal outputs and individual users' expectations to develop possible new innovative products/processes in the food-packaging sector².

Fig.1 main steps to the definition of the brokerage event scoreboard

In a first analysis, the macro steps necessary for the collection of the information were identified; in particular, three different moments have been placed in which to obtain information: the profiling of users from the database of the participants, the initial expectations of the participants and the results deriving from the follow-up, as indicated in fig. 1.

For user profiling, we have assumed to include information related to the individual and the sector/market in which the company operates, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Profiling User Information

² Zolkiewski, J., Story, V.M., Burton, J., Chan, P., Gomes, A., Hunter-Jones, P., O'Malley, L., Peters, L., Raddats, C., and Robinson, W. (Forthcoming 2017) "Strategic B2B Customer Experience Management: The Importance of Outcomes-Based Measures", Journal of Services Marketing, V.31, 2. DOI: 10.1108/JSM-10-2016-0350

The information related to the user and organization expectations before the conference and the results related to the follow-up were identified, from some specific sensitive macro-areas, such as the organization of an online/physical event and the participation of guest lectures and the general assessment of B2B brokerage event and related services (Fig. 3).

By identifying these aspects, a focus group with the project partners' participation has been developed on the one hand to choose, to assess and to calibrate the main performance indicators (fig. 4), on the other to consider the monitoring feasibility, and reduce information redundancy compliance with the project scoreboard. The relative targets have been identified for some indicators. However, we have considered the possibility of introducing future new performance indicators. Indeed, especially in the current situation, characterized by uncertainty due to the Covid-19 emergency, we have considered the chance to get future feedback and expand the scoreboard, as feedback involves a new understanding or reframing of a situation and leads to new goals and decision rules^{3 4}. In this way, we aim to counteract the risk of getting a myopic vision in performance measurement⁵.

³ J. Sterman, Business dynamics : systems thinking and modeling for a complex world. Boston ; London: Irwin/McGraw-Hill, 2000,

⁴ Argyris C. 1977. Double-loop learning in organizations. Harv. Bus. Rev. 55:115–25

⁵ van Thiel, S, & Leeuw, F.L. (2002). The Performance Paradox in the Public Sector. Public Performance and Management Review, 25(3), 267–281

Fig. 3 Comparing Expectation and Outcome

Indicators	Description	Target	M3	M6	M9	M12	M15	M18	M21	M24	Total to date
Survey to SME (during Event and Follow - Up)		2									
Overall organization evaluation by Participants (Survey)		60%									
number of b2b meeting carried out											
Number of new contacts											
number of concrete business/project opportunities,											
number testimonial from the SMEs on their participation to the activity (agenda Event)											
Number of Programmes for Internationalization Missions created (page 7)		2									
Number of Calls for applications for travel voucher launched (page 7)		2									
Advisor Board Created		1		x							
% of Capacity covered during the Event (physical event)		50%									
% of Confirmed Physical Participants		50%									
% of Confirmed Online Participants		30%									
Estimated probability to have a Follow - up b2b by the Participants (survey)		10%									
Number of Social media Followes per Social Media Platform (Twitter)											
Number of Social media Followes per Social Media Platform (Linkedin)											
Number of Social media Followes per Social Media Platform (Facebook)											

Fig. 4 Current Event Scoreboard

6. Conclusions

We expect that the use of the project monitoring scoreboard will enable the whole consortium to stay on time and to collaborate, in order to get the best results within the proposed timing. Moreover, the workflow designed as a basis of survey for SMEs participating to the events will serve as a starting point for evaluating the efficacy of the events and for acquiring lessons learned from them.